

Demande d'Attribution de Ressources Informatiques

Description scientifique du projet

1 Informations générales

Titre du Projet : 3-D seismic wave propagation modelling from the fault to the site for realistic earthquake scenarios SEM3DonGPU.

Numéro du dossier : AD010414346 (TMP29489)

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Structure de recherche : Université Paris Saclay, CentraleSupélec, CNRS, ENS Paris-Saclay, Laboratoire de Mécanique Paris-Saclay UMR 9026

Nombre d'heures demandées sur le projet :

IDRIS HPE Jean Zay A100 : 30000 heures GPU

2 Résumé

This project aims at testing the high-fidelity 3-D earthquake simulator SEM3D (patented [1, 55] and open source) on GPU. SEM3D simulates an earthquake in solid-fluid domain, from active faults to free surface, across urban regions $\approx 100 \text{ km} \times 100 \text{ km} \times 100 \text{ km}$ large, as sketched in Figure 1. The objective of this proposal is to extensively test the newly developed GPU version of the ear-

SOURCE-TO-STRUCTURE ANALYSIS

$$Y_{P_O}(f) = E(M; f) \cdot P(R; f) \quad Y_{P_T}(f) = E(M; f) \cdot P(R; f) \cdot G(f)$$

FIGURE 1 – Sketch of the source-to-structure earthquake simulations at regional scale. $E(M; f)$: earthquake source (active fault), depending on the magnitude M and the frequency content f (limited by the size of the mesh); $P(R; f)$: scattering/attenuation effect on the earthquake wave field due to propagation path P within the Earth's crust; $G(f)$: non-linear site-effects induced by the shallow softer soil layers on the propagating elastic waves. P_T : monitoring point at free surface, close to structural components (near-field) and polluted by the wave field scattered by the soil-structure interaction; P_O : monitoring point at free surface, on hard bedrock, sufficiently far away from the structural components, supposedly neither influenced by site effects nor by structural back-scattering.

thquake engine, namely SEM3D-GPU, to assess :

1. the feasibility of adopting SEM3D-GPU to participate to the international SMATCH benchmark¹, whose goal is to perform blind *stress tests* of isolated Nuclear Power Plant (NPP) submitted to realistic earthquakes ;
2. the benefit of using SEM3D-GPU to extend the open-source synthetic earthquake datasets HEMEW-3D and HEMEW^S-3D² that we produced in 2023, in collaboration with the CEA (and leveraging TGCC resources).

The scientific interests behind the latter two points are multifold. Extending the existing open access databases of earthquake ground motions (with corresponding geology and source) will be vital to train advanced machine learning and artificial intelligence surrogate models, such as our recent F-FNO (Factorized Fourier Neural Operator) described in [2]. The goal is to assess the computational cost of extending HEMEW-3D and HEMEW^S-3D, which include more than 30000 instances each³, but that would benefit from the addition of new realistic scenarios, accurate on a larger frequency range and covering larger regions, possibly including topography instead of flat surface. On the other hand, we need to assess the I/O best practices to unleash the increased speed-up and size-up of SEM3D-GPU, whose performance bottleneck seems to be related to the I/O operations to store the results. This aspect is crucial from a scientific standpoint and it demands some further testing and development. The allocation will steer the choice of the a trade-off between speed-up and snapshotting frequency when dealing with large test cases.

3 Présentation générale

3.1 General Context

Earthquakes are one of the most complex natural phenomena for scientists to understand and predict. The cogency of improved seismic hazard assessment (SHA) is motivated by the high uncertainty on the originating mechanisms, coupled with their disaster potential, increased portfolio exposure and structural demand. SHA can be assessed by either following a deterministic approach (DSHA), or by either considering a fully probabilistic approach (PSHA). While the former consists into a conservative direct modelling of the most intense ground shaking scenario, the latter bears on the statistics drawn from previous strong ground motion observations) [3]. In this context, many historical strong ground motion events have been successfully reproduced by employing *physics-based* numerical simulations (PBSs) [4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12]. PBSs provide great insights on the intricacies of earthquakes' anatomy, characterizing the 3-D seismic wave motion in near-fault conditions (including possible directivity effects) and including the complex interactions with the surface topography and the geological settings (surface waves, wave trapping within basin-like structures). This achievement has been made possible by the development of high-fidelity/high-performance numerical codes, successfully deployed on large supercomputer infrastructures. As an example, an impressive result was obtained by a Chinese research group, who run a non-linear earthquake simulation over a continental 320 km by 312 km by 40 km region, up to 18 Hz [13]. The use of octrees has made possible a high degree of scalability in mesh generation using up to 220.000 cores [14]. Recent studies [15, 16] have paved the way to the use of PBS, traditionally employed for DSHA, in PSHA too, via optimized scheduling and scenario sampling techniques. Moreover, high-fidelity PBS widened the research horizons concerning the

1. Seismic Base Isolated Nuclear Power Plant Shaken by a Real Earthquake (SMATCH), see <https://smatch-benchmark.org/>. The benchmark is organized by IRSN (Institut de Radioprotection et de Sûreté Nucléaire) and EDF (Électricité de France), under the umbrella of OECD-NEA (Nuclear Energy Agency).

2. Available at recherche.data.gouv.fr.

3. In HEMEW-3D, only the variability on the geological setups are considered, whereas in HEMEW^S-3D, both variability on geology and source location/characteristics are investigated.

study of complex features such as the attenuation and coherency of coda wave in the seismic signals [17], the directivity and the incoherence of the near-source wave motion [18] and non-linear site effects [19] among others. The advent of exascale computing is fostering the development of integrated end-to-end earthquake simulators and seismic *digital shadows*⁴ for critical structures and infrastructures [21], capable of provide reliable and quasi-real-time seismic risk prediction and structural response, as well as updated seismic hazard maps for regulatory public policies.

In areas of moderate seismicity, such as metropolitan France, a general lack of direct seismic observations limits clashes with the demand of updated seismic safety margins for critical structures and infrastructures (nuclear power plants and dams especially). Given the fact that the majority of them has been constructed a few decades ago, French authorities face the urgency of a general reassessment of the seismic safety margins foreseen at the design stage, exploiting the gathered knowledge in seismology, earthquake engineering, the new geophysical and geological data, as well as the new technological tools available. Nuclear facilities, dams and other important infrastructures must undergo extensive *stress testing*, to assess and update their status and functionality, in case an unexpected (at the design stage) earthquake occurs. Moreover, those *stress tests* must include complex soil-structure interaction that were neglected in the past (surface waves, near-field conditions) in favor of more conservative design choices. This commitment fosters the definition of site-specific studies (the Cadarache nuclear site for instance) which can now be virtually tested via high-fidelity *digital shadows*. This is the general context of the SMATCH international benchmark focusing on a seismic base-isolated Nuclear Power Plant (NPP) submitted to a realistic earthquake.

One major obstacle hindering the extensive use of synthetic ground shaking response in structural design is PBS limitation to a relatively low frequency interval, reaching maximum accuracies beyond 1 Hz, but up to 10 Hz. However, the vibration footprint of critical above-ground structures and related non-structural system components (such as piping systems and other equipment) are characterized by resonant eigenmodes way above 5 Hz [22]) and up until 40 Hz. The reasons behind this discrepancy between fault-to-site and site-to-structure simulations are two, namely : (i) the increasing computational demand implied by finer non-aliasing spatial discretization, required to simulate wave interactions at shorter wavelengths; (ii) the large uncertainty on the underground geological and seismotectonic configuration (the mechanical properties of huge chunks of Earth's crust, including shallow soil non-linearity [23], the geometry of the geological interfaces between layers [24], the geometry of active fault segments, their roughness, properties and tectonic stress acting on them before the earthquake occurs), preventing the accurate calibration of the numerical model.

The project proposal is meant to be a follow-up of 2023 and 2024 IDRIS Open Hackathons on GPU, that allowed to port the earthquake engine, SEM3D on GPU. SEM3D-CPU has extensively been used in previous DARI allocations, allowing to explore regional earthquake scenarios for different sites of interest, among which the experimental site of Argostoli [27, 28] and the Cadarache ITER nuclear facilities, located in the tectonic region dominated by the system of active faults of Middle Durance (MDF), in South-Eastern France [24, 29]. The latter model was constructed and validated in allocation A8 : two models were constructed, with different mesh refinement (see Table 1). However, those studies were performed on CPU nodes, with the CPU version of SEM3D-CPU, while waiting to stabilize its GPU version, started during the 2023 edition of the Open Hackathon. Dynamic access TMP29489 (issued after the 2023 Hackathon) was meant to complete the SEM3D-CPU porting on GPU, but it had partially been exploited differently, due to code-managing issues. Thanks to Open Hackathon 2024 edition, SEM3D-GPU can now be used in more realistic test cases,

4. According to [20], in a digital shadow, data flow is unidirectional from physical to digital twin.

tag	No. □ Elements [10 ⁶]	GLL	DOFs [10 ⁹]	f_{\max}
#1	≈3.8	5 × 5 × 5	≈1.44	5
#2	≈13.2	5 × 5 × 5	≈4.94	10

TABLE 1 – Characteristics of the Cadarache numerical models constructed and validated with the computational resources of this allocation.

which, according to us, justifies the extension of the dynamic allocation we ask for in this proposal.

Albeit the outstanding results obtained by high-performance computing in *physics-based* modeling, due to its ontological determinism and to the large computational costs at stake, the methodology is still hardly adaptable to tackle large parameter sweeps, provided with the mentioned high level of uncertainty, convolved with the numerical dispersion. Our first attempt in this sense was made with HEMEW-3D and HEMEW^S-3D datasets [25], where we simulated 0-5 Hz accurate earthquake scenarios over a rather small 9 km × 9 km × 9 km region. This endeavour allowed explore how the source and geological uncertainty propagates through the model and how to attempt at reducing it (the choice of *eigen-geologies* [26]) and to quantify seismic risk assessment of critical structures by exploiting synthetic time histories.

3.2 Perspectives on AI-assisted physics-based earthquake generation on Jean-Zay

The activity report shows how we could successfully make use of part of the dynamic allocation, to develop complementary AI tools that SEM3D-CPU simulations could feed (see *Rapport d'activité*). Among those AI tools, the dynamic allocation focused on developing a Generative Adversarial Network framework for complementing the 5-30 Hz frequency spectrum of a SEM3D-CPU simulation (Gottfried Jacquet's PhD Thesis). The dynamic allocation allowed to test several GAN architectures (for a total approximately 440M parameters for the generators and 220M parameters per discriminator), such as ALICE (Adversarially Learning Inference and Cross Entropy) [30], Pix2Pix (signal-to-signal translation), BicycleGAN (Bidirectional Cycle Generative Adversarial Network) [31], and MUST-ALICE (Multi-modal Unsupervised Signal Translation ALICE, shown in Figure 2), in order to be able to achieve super-resolution earthquake generation in a one-to-many framework (a SEM3D-CPU simulation, represented by 3-components time histories $\mathbf{x}(t)$ (valid in 0-1 Hz frequency range) for several seismograms at broadband 0-30 Hz $\mathbf{y}(t)$).

The results presented in Figure 2 were obtained thanks to an improved training stability of the GAN framework, on ≈128000 seismic recordings of 4096 time steps each. This achievement was granted by the possibility of exploiting a larger number of GPU per job (under a Distributed Data Parallel paradigm) on Jean-Zay and a mini-batch size 4 times larger than the feasible mini-batch size on Université Paris-Saclay's cluster (16 signals maximum). Jean-Zay's GPU resources allowed us to specifically address the open question of disentangling the latent variables representing an encoded version of the earthquake ground motion time series, either simulated via PBS, either recorded.

3.3 Research perspectives for this proposal

According to what stated in the summary (see Section 2), the present proposal is devoted to the research goals detailed in the following paragraphs.

FIGURE 2 – Example of result for the Multi-modal Signal Translation. (a) List of time-frequency Envelope and Phase Goodness of Fit (EG and PG respectively, see [32]) for the MUST architecture. The target is represented by the recorded earthquake time histories at each station, namely $y(t)$ (black signals). The MUST-ALICE input is the PBS simulation (obtained, for instance, via SEM3D-CPU) (b) One-to-many super-resolved earthquake time histories, obtained from SEM3D-CPU simulation x and with MUST-ALICE generative framework. x is encoded by a deep conformer architecture F_{xy} , branched into a disentangled latent representation : F_{xy}^c for the common features to both PBS $x(t)$ and records $y(t)$, the other for the *high-frequency* features of y . The latent representation is decoded by G_y residual decoder with conformer and *AdaIn* layers. (c-e) Variants of the generated signal $G_y(F_{xy}^c(x), \mathcal{N}(0, I))$, where the *high-frequency* features of y are sampled from white noise.

SMATCH benchmark So far, very rare are the examples of complete fault-to-structure interaction studies, with strong Soil-Structure Interaction coupling (see for instance [33, 34, 35, 21]). In allocation A8 and A10, PBS has been used for models #1 and #2 in Table 1, improving to be able to properly model the interactions between the basin-like sedimentary deposits underneath the ITER facility at Cadarache and the input wave motion, generated by the nearby extended fault ($\approx 14 \text{ km} \times 7 \text{ km}$) [36]. In last years, we developed (in collaboration with EDF R&D) a pipeline chaining scheme to use SEM3D-CPU regional simulations as input motion for commercial code of

structural dynamics (i.e., `code_aster`, developed by EDF itself) and to simulate a fault-to-structure earthquake scenario with the so called Domain Reduction Method (DRM, see Figure 3), proposed by Bielak et al. [37]. It consists into a two-step analysis, declined as follows (see Figure 3) : (i) regional scale wave-propagation in simplified geological medium (typically the deep visco-elastic stratified Earth’s crust), not including the non-linear site-effects; (ii) a second run of the analysis on a smaller domain (eventually adding the structure) delimited by an artificial boundary at which equivalent inertial forces and free-field velocities, obtained in the precedent step, are applied. [38] applied this method to study the structural response of the Kashiwazaki-Kariwa

FIGURE 3 – Schematic representation of the domain reduction method (adopted by [37]). (a) Reference problem ; (b) backbone regional problem ; (c) reduced domain problem.

Nuclear Power Plant (KKNPP) in a fault-to-structure framework, up to 1 Hz. [39, 21] developed the EQSIM platform for exascale computing of structural response via DRM.

Thanks to the collaboration with EDF R&D and previous allocations A8 and A10, we managed to reproduce realistic fault-to-structure earthquake simulations with both `code_aster` and `Cast3m`. One major goal of this proposal is to employ the GPU version of the earthquake engine, namely `SEM3D-GPU` to improve this tool-chain coupling multiple softwares, in the occasion of the above-mentioned SMATCH international benchmark. The allocation will help finalizing the set of validation benchmarks (started during the 2024 IDRIS Hackathon) on the new GPU version of the code and to assess the feasibility of using it as a valid and more efficient alternative to its CPU version.

Improving AI tools for earthquake generator at super-resolution MUST-ALICE training was performed in supervised way, by adopting the 3-components seismic records $(\mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{y}(t))$ belonging STEAD dataset [40]. Since we did not have the possibility of running a simulation per each recorded sample, we low-pass-filtered the latter, namely $\mathbf{y}(t)$ to 1 Hz, to obtain $\mathbf{x}(t)$. The underlying assumption is that PBS resemble to a filtered version of the recorded time histories. In the meanwhile, we also created two large datasets (HEMEW-3D and HEMEW^S-3D, i.e. `SEM3D-CPU` simulations, accurate up to 5 Hz, considering randomly heterogeneous geological domains and with randomly chosen source point positions and characteristics) to be used as purely synthetic data $\mathbf{x}(t)$ and to test MUST-ALICE framework in a blind predictive scheme. Therefore, the second objective of this proposal is to finally be able to validate MUST-ALICE by extending HEMEW-3D and HEMEW^S-3D to a larger frequency range and to even more realistic geological profiles and source types by adopting `SEM3D-GPU`, whose initial performances are listed below.

4 Méthode

4.1 Méthode numérique et implémentations (CPU version `SEM3D-CPU`)

We actively develop (jointly with CEA and Insitut de Physique du Globe de Paris) an efficient multi-tool computational tool, called `SEM3D-CPU` [1, 55], capable of simulating broad-band non-

linear seismic wave propagation in highly heterogeneous media, from the fault to the above-ground structures. [41] compiled a table summarizing major large-scale time-domain simulations of seismic wave motion. Table 2 partially reports the mentioned table and it integrates the table compiled by [13] to show a panorama of the most significant earthquake simulations performed in the last 10 years. The simulation indicated as A7 in Table 2 corresponds to an earthquake sce-

Ref.	Year	Method	Ressources	DOFs	Grid Size (m)	Size (km×km×km)	f_{\max} (Hz)	Topography
[42]	2010	FDM	6 CPUs	-	25/125	-	2.5	no
	2010	SEM	32 CPUs	66187872	150	-	2.0	yes
	2010	SEM	63 CPUs	39902676	20-900	-	3.0	yes
	2010	dG	510 CPUs	-	200-5000	-	3.0	yes
[43]	2010	FEM	-	251457147	var	600×300×80	0.5	no
	2010	FDM	-	2.355 billions	200	500×250×50	0.5	no
	2010	FDM	-	5.419 billions	100	600×300×80	0.5	no
[44]	2010	SEM	192 GPU	131000256	-	chunk of earth	0.7	no
[45]	2010	FDM	-	1308 billions	40	810×405×85	2.0	no
[46]	2012	SEM	896 GPU	22 billions	24000	Western Europe× 200	0.125	yes
[7]	2013	FEM	24000 CPUs	15.9 billions	5.5 88	180×135×32	4.0	no
[47]	2014	dG	1400832 CPUs	96 billions	-	-	10	yes
[48]	2017	FEM	294912 CPUs	10.7 billions	0.66	2 × 2 × 0.1	-	yes
[13]	2017	FDM	1014000 CPUs	23.4 trillions	8	320×312×40	18	yes
[21]	2020	FDM	131072 CPUs	8.88 billions	8	100×40×30	5	no
A7	2020	SEM	4000 CPUs	13.5 billions	35 130	44 × 44 × 63	10	no

TABLE 2 – Summary of major time-domain, large-scale simulations of seismic waves in the last 10 years (table after [41]). FDM : Finite Different Method, FEM : Finite Element Method, SEM : Spectral Element Method, dG : discontinuous Galerkin. "-" indicates that the desired data is not available in the reference.

nario of the Argostoli experimental site, performed on Occigen during allocation A7 [27, 49]. As a matter of fact, Table 2 highlights the fact that SEM3D-CPU represents a competitive alternative to modern broad-band synthetic earthquake simulators world-wide, considering the valuable accuracy relatively to the *limited* computational resources employed.

The core of the platform is represented by a Spectral Element (SE) Method code, tailored to solve 3-D wave propagation in anisotropic, randomly heterogeneous and non-linear geo-materials. The experimental design (ED) foreseen for this project is constructed by SEM3D-CPU analyses. However, the platform is featured by a series of other computational tools that help in constructing large scale numerical scenario of an earthquake event, namely :

- HexMesh⁵ : a scalable octree-based mesh generation code ;
- randomField⁶ : a scalable random field generator over large computational domains, based on the spectral generation technique [50].

The parallel octree-based mesh generator is able to treat immersed geometries with high scalability in executions. It was tested up to 6561 processing CPUs. The mesh can be non-conforming, composed exclusively by hexahedrons, or it can be made conforming using tetrahedral elements. Non-conforming meshes have hanging nodes, (i.e. nodes located inside edges or faces), which restricts its use to numerical methods that provide support for this type of nodal interpolation. In particular, efficient parallel implementation of the SEM requires the use of conformal hexahedra. Owing to the SEM spectral convergence, higher resolution is obtained by p -refinement (i.e. by increasing the polynomial order) rather than by increasing the number of linear elements (common practice in Finite Difference/Element schemes).

The random field generator employs the sum of a series of N_ϕ cosines with random phases and random amplitudes [51], sampled over fine regular grids [23]. The Fast Fourier Transform can be used to bring the complexity of this generation method to $\mathcal{O}(N_\phi \log N_\phi)$. The field is then re-interpolated over the not uniformly space-distributed SE grid (featured by 5 to 10 Gauss-Lobatto-Legendre points per dimension). When dealing with large domains, the scalability issue is solved

5. <https://github.com/jcamata/HexMesh.git>

6. <https://github.com/cottureau/randomField.git>

by generating smaller independent realizations, supported on overlapping subdomains (in a distributed memory parallel scheme), and then recomposed together into the full domain. Finally, the non-linear wave-propagation solver exploits the high resolution of the spectral element method with efficient explicit algorithm to integrate non-linear rheology representing the non-linear cyclic behaviour of soils.

In the following, the peculiar features of the mentioned computational platform are described.

4.1.1 Octree-based Mesh Generation : HexMesh

Octrees are hierarchical data structures that allows the decomposition a three-dimensional space in regular cubes, called octants. The initial octant normally surrounds all the input domain and is divided in 8 equally spaced cubes - the child octants. Each of these children could be subdivided again, in a recursive process that is usually limited by some criteria (i.e. maximum number of subdivisions, minimum octant size). An octree can be implemented by a tree structure or by a linear octree, where only octants with no children are stored. In this last representation, as also known by linear octree, each leaf is stored as a unique integer - called locational code - which identifies its position and depth level in the tree. Among the benefits of linear octrees is the implicit representation of intermediary octants (non-leaves), making it memory efficient, and better performance on sequential access. Additionally, by not making use of memory pointers, parallel implementation of the linear octree has a lower overhead in interprocess communication (in comparison to other tree structures [52]). We have implemented a set of algorithms that address the special needs of parallel octree meshing. These algorithms are : (i) Octree initialization algorithm that guarantees that all processes have at least one piece of the linear octree. (ii) Refinement algorithm that decompose the octants according to some refinement criterion (i.e. maximum size or position relative to the geometry boundaries), and 2 :1 balancing algorithm that ensure that no neighbor octants differentiate in more than one level [52]. This last algorithm is important because a balanced octree results in more smooth transitions between elements, a feature that has a direct influence on the final mesh quality. It also guarantees that the resulting mesh will not have more than one hanging node for each edge or face, reducing the complexity of conforming mesh process. The resulting code has been written in plain C and makes use of MPI only. The code runs on any standard cluster. A previous version of the code (generating non-conformal hexahedra and conformal tetrahedra meshes) has been tested at Stampede Dell cluster (at TACC) and on a SGI ICE 8400 and on a Oracle cluster in Brazil. Table 3 presents a weak scalability test performed on the mesh of the Kefalonia region (Greece). The communication time (last column) attains a fairly constant percentage of the total time. The code has run over 6561 MPI processes.

Cores	Levels	Nodes	Elements	Time (s)	Comm(%)
81	7	85,602,744	83,102,679	12.061	21 %
243	8	769,790,232	747,937,476	32.994	20 %
729	9	6,926,153,724	6,731,438,013	105.188	25 %
6561	10	62,330,385,168	60,583,119,264	123.066	29 %

TABLE 3 – Weak scaling of the mesh generation for the Kefalonia region in Greece. Cores : number of MPI processes ; Levels : octree refinement level ; Nodes : number of mesh nodes ; Elements : number of mesh elements ; Time : generation time ; Comm : percentage of the total elapsed time for communication operation.

Figure 4 show an example of a mesh generated by HexMesh.

FIGURE 4 – Mesh of the Cadarache region [29].

4.1.2 Random Field Generation : `randomField`

The heterogeneous properties of the Earth’s crust are included in our modelling strategy for large scale earthquake scenarios. In this context, by *large* we refer to a domain size L much larger than both the correlation length ℓ_C (or some characteristic size of the fluctuation) and the discretization step h . It is therefore advantageous to represent those fluctuations a scalar random fields (for instance, representing the spatial distribution of the shear-modulus). Those large random fields can be effectively sampled over a coarse grid (with a step size relevant for the correlation length) and then interpolated onto the mesh of interest (provided by the GLL (Gauss-Lobatto-Legendre) grid used in SEM3D-CPU). If the discretization step is much larger than the correlation length, the sampling becomes simple and numerically inexpensive. Indeed, for the mesh considered, the random field is essentially a white noise with Gaussian first-order marginal density [53]. The first-order marginal density is modified locally by combining a direct and inverse Rosenblatt transforms [54]. `randomField` uses the spectral quadrature formula proposed by [51] to generate the random field, taking advantage of the Fast Fourier Transform algorithms (using the library FFTW⁷). The code is written in Fortran95 and exploits HDF5 data structures for I/O operations. To efficiently reduce the generation time for large L/ℓ_C values, `randomField` is implemented in a highly-scalable *localized* fashion, exploiting MPI. Independent realizations are generated over subdomains, that are then recomposed into the whole domain, by smoothing the discontinuities at the boundaries between partitions to preserve the correlation structure.

Table 4 lists the results of the scalability test performed on `randomField`, with the *standard* and *localized* approaches respectively (i.e. by generating a unique random field over the entire domain (*standard* approach) or by generating independent realizations over subdomains (*localized* approach)). This scalability test was performed by running the generation code on Occigen cluster.

4.1.3 Non-linear wave propagation : SEM3D-CPU

SEM3D-CPU [1, 55] is mainly conceived for applications in geophysics, with the aim of considering realistic 3-D complex geo-structures. It is written in Fortran 95, and uses MPI. The I/O is performed using parallel HDF5 libraries. The meshes are non-structured and composed of conformal hexahedra by employing METIS⁸ library. The discretization in space is based on spectral elements in space and an explicit scheme in time (both for elastic and non-linear case). The spectral element

7. <http://fftw.org/>

8. <http://glaros.dtc.umn.edu/gkhome/views/metis>

Cores	Nodes	Generation Time (s)	
		Standard	Localized
16	1×10^6	0.86	6.57
32	2×10^6	1.55	13.87
256	2×10^7	356.43	159.98
2048	1×10^8	–	2037.48
4096	3×10^8	–	3299.04

TABLE 4 – Weak scalability analysis for the random field generation (Machine : Occigen Intel E5-2690 (2.6 GHz) / $\sim 50 \times 10^3$ cores). Standard : wall-time required to generate a single random field over the entire domain. Localized : wall-time time required to generate the random field with the localized approach mentioned in the text.

method is a variant of the finite element methods which uses high-order Lagrange polynomials on Gauss-Lobatto-Legendre (GLL) points. The corresponding quadrature ensures that the mass matrix is diagonal. Hence, inversion of the mass matrix at each time steps is not costly and very short time steps, imposed by the explicit scheme, are not an issue. The code was tested on several clusters, including Curie (by CEA) and the Mésocentre de CentraleSupélec and ENS Paris Saclay (SGI ICE X) and GENCI CINES BULL Occigen (c20150447417, A0040410444, A0060410444, A0070411083, A0080410444) and IDRIS HPE Jean Zay CSL (A0080410444). Moreover, it has been run on the 64-nodes Bi-Opteron cluster of Service de Calcul Parallèle de l’Institut de Physique du Globe de Paris (a model with 25 millions degrees of freedom, running over 128 CPUs). A previous version of the code (less efficient in terms of parallelism [56]) was tested on Jade, in a previous GENCI project (c2010046485). On these occasions, the weak scalability of the spectral element solver has been demonstrated. Finally, it should be noted that a code with similar features and structure (although developed by a completely different team) was ported on the largest clusters available (see for example [57], 15 years back).

An example of weak scalability curve obtained for SEM3D-CPU is shown in Figure 6a. SEM3D-CPU has been run over more than 4096 CPUs. SEM3D-CPU is based upon RegSEM code [58, 59] and compared to RegSEM, an asynchronous communication scheme is employed. Moreover, data structures are stored in a way that promotes vectorization, as schematically depicted in Figure 5

FIGURE 5 – Vectorization scheme. (a) Non-vectorized i, j, k, e storing order. (b) Vectorized ee, i, j, k, b order, with $ee = e \bmod 4$ and $b = e/4$.

Internal forces are computed at each iteration, over loops of fixed lengths, 4 or 8 respectively and established at compilation time. This setup naturally accommodates for viscoelastic and non-linear constitutive relationships : in SEM3D-CPU, a generalized Zener model is implemented [60], as much as a simple non-linear rheological model [23]. The improvements made to the original RegSEM led to a considerable code speed-up as Figure 6b witnesses.

In [49], the author performed the verification and validation tests proposed by [61] for the E2VP

FIGURE 6 – (a) Weak scalability curves obtained for SEM3D-CPU, expressed as number of time rate of mesh elements processed varying the number of MPI process employed. In blue, the linear scalability curve represents the ideal *optimum* result (perfectly linear scalability). Green and red lines portray the *worst* and *average* performances instead. (b) Improvement of SEM3D-CPU compared to initial RegSEM version. The values of CPU time refer to the equivalent-mono-core time required to solve a wave-propagation problem in a $600\text{ m} \times 600\text{ m} \times 600\text{ m}$ cube, with PML on all sides and $5 \times 5 \times$ GLL per element of size $50\text{ m} \times 50\text{ m}$.

benchmark⁹. Moreover, given the experience of recent allocations on Occigen, a comparison between SEM3D-CPU performances obtained on Fusion (cluster of Mésocentre Moulon) and Occigen was drawn, to check our estimations in terms of required CPU-hours. Ten simulations are hereafter compared : F1-F5, run on Fusion, O1-O5, run on Occigen (see the specifics in Table 5). Figure 7 shows the performances obtained, compared to the original (CP) and corrected-blind (BP) prediction (made before allocation A4). First and foremost, we noticed a very good agreement between the corrected prediction CP and F1 and BP and F4, which justifies our prediction made on Fusion. However, we needed some preliminary iterations (corresponding to simulations O1-O3) to replicate the same performances obtained on Fusion (in terms of CPU-time). Specifically, preliminary simulations O1-O3 (performed without the CINES support, before the mid-term allocation) showed a increased computation burden (expressed as *ratio-to-result* $\frac{t_{CPU}}{t_{EQK}}$). For instance, O2 and F4 represents the same simulation, although we obtained a CPU-time per second real time simulation $\frac{t_{CPU}}{t_{EQK}} [h/s]$ of 1.82×10^3 h/s for Fusion and 3.49×10^4 h/s for Occigen respectively. Iterations O4-O5 were performed thanks to the CINES support : the same performances were obtained for Fusion and Occigen on the same test case : $\frac{t_{CPU}}{t_{EQK}} = 1.772 \cdot 10^3$ h/s for Occigen vs $\frac{t_{CPU}}{t_{EQK}} [h/s]$ of 1.82×10^3 h/s for Fusion. This iteration validates SEM3D-CPU portability on Occigen. In the following, we transitioned towards a higher number of DOFs by improving the numerical model of Argostoli (see the mesh characteristics in Table 6), previously run on Fusion (F5). On Occigen, the same numerical model was considered (called O5), its accuracy being increased by *p*-refinement, i.e. by increasing two times the GLL points per edge (resulting in $10 \times 10 \times 10$ GLL points per element), for a total $\approx 13.48 \cdot 10^9$. We successfully simulated a 20 sec earthquake strong ground motion, consuming around 81100 CPU hours (*ratio-to-result* . For O5-F5, we also included the new code feature represented by the extended fault seismic source. Expected performances were attained (quasi-linear scalability) and we successfully passed the limit of 10^{10} DOFs (never before achieved

9. The reference solution was uploaded on the SISMOWINE interactive seismological web interface used for numerical modeling benchmarking <http://sismowine.org>. *HSP1a*, *Can2* and *Can4* benchmarks were performed by [49].

FIGURE 7 – CPU-time per real earthquake simulation $\frac{t_{CPU}}{t_{EQK}}$, for different DOF numbers. BP and CP correspond to the blind and corrected-blind predictions respectively (see mid-term allocation).

	N_{EL}	N_{GLL}	N_{MPI}
F1	2×10^6	5	648
F2	-	7	648
F3	-	10	648
F4	18×10^6	5	648
F5	4.5×10^6	5	216
O1	-	5	4800
O2	-	5	648
O3	-	7	648
O4	-	5	4800
O5	4.5×10^6	5	4000
CP	2×10^6	5	216
BP	18×10^6	5	648

TABLE 5 – Earthquake numerical model. N_E : number of hexahedrons (8-nodes); N_{GLL} : number of GLL points per element); N_{MPI} : number of CPU CPUs.

N_E	N_D	$\mathcal{L}_x \cdot \mathcal{L}_y \cdot \mathcal{L}_z$ [km^3]	$\Delta_x^{min} \cdot \Delta_y^{min} \cdot \Delta_z^{min}$ [m^3]
$\approx 4.5 \cdot 10^6$	$\approx 9.8 - 13.5 \cdot 10^9$	$44 \times 44 \times 63$	$130 \times 130 \times 35$

TABLE 6 – Mesh characteristics for the earthquake scenario of Kefalonia island [62] (model O5). N_E : number of hexahedrons (8-nodes); N_D : number of Degrees of Freedom ($10 \times 10 \times 10$ GLL \times 3 per element); \mathcal{L}_x - \mathcal{L}_y - \mathcal{L}_z domain sizes; Δ_x^{min} - Δ_y^{min} - Δ_z^{min} minimum element sizes.

on Fusion), thanks to the possibility of running jobs over > 720 CPU - cores (current limitation for Fusion).

In allocation A8, we tested SEM3D-CPU on Jean Zay CSL and obtained comparable performance to those obtained on Occigen. In Figure 8, the outcome of several SEM3D-CPU runs is shown. Simulations were performed on our Mésocentre cluster (Fusion), on Occigen and on Jean Zay. JZ and O3 are two runs of Cadarache model #2 mentioned above, performed on 8000 MPI processes and 4000 MPI processes respectively, with similar CPU (mono-core) hours t_{CPU} per second of simulated earthquake t_{EQK} .

Finally, a heuristic rule of thumb was inferred from previous experience : optimal performances were observed when 10000 hexahedrons, each featured by $N_{GLL} = 5 \times 5 \times 5$, are processed per node, considering a standard node memory of 2 Gb.

4.1.4 SEM3D-GPU

IDRIS Open Hackathons 2023 and 2024¹⁰ helped us porting SEM3D-CPU on GPU, by leveraging OpenACC. SEM3D-GPU was compiled on Jean-Zay A100 and V100 GPU, with nvidia-compilers/24.3. The preliminary comparisons with SEM3D-CPU are shown in Figure 9, which refers to a test case of approximately 8 millions hexahedrons with 125 integration point each ($\approx 3 \cdot 10^9$ DOFs).

Two interesting aspects can be highlighted : 512 MPI processes are efficiently replaced by 8 A100 GPU, with a speedup factor of ≈ 3.34 . Another interest in switching to the GPU version is pro-

10. This work was completed in part at the IDRIS Open Hackathon, part of the Open Hackathons program. The authors would like to acknowledge OpenACC-Standard.org for their support.

FIGURE 8 – CPU-time per real earthquake simulation t_{CPU}/t_{EQK} , for different DOF numbers.

INPUTS		Runtime (s)	
# CPU Cores	512		1638
# GPUs (A100)	8		490
Application Speedup	3.5x		3.34285714285714
Node Replacement	14.0x		
GPU NODE POWER SAVINGS			
	AMD Dual Rome 7H12	8x A100 80GB SXM4	Power Savings
Compute Power (W)	15,400	6,500	8,900
Networking Power (W)	650	93	557
Total Power (W)	16,050	6,593	9,457
Node Power efficiency	2.4x		
ANNUAL ENERGY SAVINGS PER GPU NODE			
	AMD Dual Rome 7H12	8x A100 80GB SXM4	Power Savings
Compute Power (kWh/year)	134,904	56,940	77,964
Networking Power (kWh/year)	5,695	814	4,881
Total Power (kWh/year)	140,599	57,754	82,845
\$/kWh	\$ 0.34		
Annual Cost Savings	\$ 28,167.45		
3-year Cost Savings	\$ 84,502.34		
Metric Tons of CO ₂	59		
Gasoline Cars Driven for 1 year	13		
Seedlings Trees grown for 10 years	971		

FIGURE 9 – Comparison between SEM3D-GPU and SEM3D-CPU on Jean-Zay NVIDIA A100 GPU.

vided by the node power efficiency increase by a factor 2.4, with a relatively large cost saving and reduction of equivalent CO₂ emissions, as shown in Figure 9. Moreover, nsight profiling revealed that the test case occupied 33 GB/GPU A100 node on Jean Zay. This avoids the memory-boundedness that would hinder the speedup.

Figure 10 shows the impact of I/O operations : despite being the time-marching scheme almost perfectly overlapped (with asynchronous streams), the I/O operations (red bars in Figure 10a) are synchronous blocking operations, required to save the results (snapshots).

Some further development (started but not finalized during the 2024 Open Hackathon) is required

(a)

(b)

FIGURE 10 – nsight profiling results obtained for the test case in Figure 9. Red bar indicate I/O operations.

to store snapshots and traces (currently offloaded from GPU to CPU every iteration) on GPU memory at run time and asynchronously flush and save them on disk at snapshotting time.

4.2 Justification de l'usage des ressources sur la machine demandée

We believe that the performances described in Section 4.1.4 justify the interest of using the GPU version for the scientific plan we have in mind. The earthquake simulation time considered in Figure 9 was $t_{EQK} = 0.025$ s, whereas simulation wall time was approximately 492 s, for a total of $t_{GPU} = 492 \text{ s} * 8 \approx 1 \text{ h}$ GPU-equivalent for SEM3D-GPU.

This finding implies that :

- running a similar test case (same amount of DOFs) for a realistic 30 s earthquake would require ≈ 1200 GPU-equivalent hours¹¹;
- test case O5 (see Section 4.1.3) is featured by $13.48/3 \approx 4.5$ degrees of freedom more than the test case ran during the Hackathon 2024 and presented in Figure 9;
- assuming perfectly linear weak scalability, simulation O5 should roughly run in $t_{GPU} = 4.5 * 1200 = 5400$ h mono-GPU equivalent (for a minimum of 4.5 nodes GPU A100)¹²
- given the time required for SEM3D-CPU to simulate one instance of the HEMEW-3D dataset, i.e., $t_{CPU} = 22.72$ mono-CPU equivalent hours (with 64 MPI cores), the same simulation would requires $22.72/3.34 = 6.8$ h on 1 GPU A100 (empirical speedup factor of 3.34 estimated in Figure 9).

Some information related to the O5 simulations are reported in Table 7 and Table 8. Table 8

N_E	N_D	$\mathcal{L}_x \cdot \mathcal{L}_y \cdot \mathcal{L}_z$ [km^3]	$\Delta_x^{\min} \cdot \Delta_y^{\min} \cdot \Delta_z^{\min}$ [m^3]
$\approx 4.5 \cdot 10^6$	$\approx 9.8 - 13.5 \cdot 10^9$	$44 \times 44 \times 63$	$130 \times 130 \times 35$

TABLE 7 – Mesh characteristics for the earthquake scenario of Kefalonia island [62] (model O5). N_E : number of hexahedrons (8-nodes); N_D : number of Degrees of Freedom ($10 \times 10 \times 10$ GLL \times 3 per element); $\mathcal{L}_x - \mathcal{L}_y - \mathcal{L}_z$ domain sizes; $\Delta_x^{\min} - \Delta_y^{\min} - \Delta_z^{\min}$ minimum element sizes.

lists the GPU computational resources estimated to perform the simulation described.

N_{GPU}	M_{GPU} [Gb]	t_{GPU} [h]	HD [Gb]	N_{FILES}
40	35	≈ 1200	≈ 3500	≈ 15000

TABLE 8 – Computational resources allocated for one simulation of the Argostoli earthquake scenario (O5 simulation in Section 4.1.3). N_{GPU} : number of GPU devices; M_{GPU} : memory per GPU device; t_{GPU} mono-processor equivalent GPU-time (for 20.0 seconds of real earthquake) computed as $walltime \times N_{GPU}$ (see Eq. 1); HD : Hard-Disk allocation; N_{FILES} : number of files generated.

HD in Table 8 refers to the total storage required for : (1) saving results (typically, 2000 Gb for velocity contour maps close to the surface topography, 5 Gb for the time histories), (2) storing mesh files and heterogeneous mechanical properties (≈ 10 -20 Gb) and to perform save&restart procedure (state variables must be saved all over the domain, which leads to around ≈ 2000 Gb). All

11. At constant DOF number, the time per iteration is the same, as well as the time-marching scheme preparation and dismissal.

12. Please note that the scalar computational time t_{GPU} represents the total elapsed GPU time as equivalent mono-GPU, i.e. it is the sum of the running times of each device in parallel, according to the equation :

$$t_{GPU} = t_{wall} \times N_{GPU} \quad (1)$$

where t_{wall} is the wall-time (also called *elapsed* time) and N_{GPU} is number of GPU A100 devices.

files saved are in HDF5 format. The amount of file generated N_{FILES} includes the protections, that are immediately erased after the run, and the mesh files, which are the same for each simulation.

In this project, we estimate a total amount of 3 O5-like simulation (for the SMATCH benchmark) of 5400 mono-GPU equivalent hours each and 2000 simulations (to enlarge the datasets for deep-learning) of 6.8 mono-GPU equivalent hours each, for a total of 29800. We aim at performing each simulation over a minimum 40 GPUs A100 (on 5 GPU nodes) and corresponding 320 CPUs cores. This choice justify the request of 30000 scalar mono-GPU equivalent hours on A100 GPU nodes (with 200 hours of trial& error setup, to complete the development, as stated in Section 4.1.4).

5 Plan de gestion de données (DMP)

In terms of memory, we need to save approximately 500 Gb of the actual 3500 Gb demanded per run (we erase the protections). Therefore we estimated 15 Tb maximum of hard-disk allocation. No permanent storage is required (data will be progressively repatriated).

Concerning visualization, we would like to have access to a GPU visualization node, with GPU accelerated paraview software. Contour plots have been effectively rendered by GPU accelerated paraview software up until 4 Tb on Occigen visualization node(Broadwell E5-2690 V4@2.6GHz, 1 GPUs Nvidia Tesla P100 PCIe 12Go).

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